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**QO'YLAR BURUN BO'SHLIG'I O'QRASI *Oestrus ovis* L.
(DIPTERA:OESTRIDAE) O'RGANILISHI**

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**ИЗУЧЕНИЕ НОСОГЛОТОЧНОГО ОВОДА ОВЕЦ *Oestrus ovis* L.
(DIPTERA:OESTRIDAE)**

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STUDY OF THE NOSOPHARNETIC GADDLE OF SHEEP *Oestrus ovis* L. (DIPTERA:OESTRIDAE)

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Калит сўзлар: Qo'ylar burun bo'shlig'i o'qrasi, *Oestrus ovis*, estroz, qarako'l qo'ylari

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In Uzbekistan, animal husbandry is a major branch of agricultural production. Sheep breeding plays an important role in the economy of our

country. In turn, astrakhan breeding occupies a large share. In terms of the number of karakul sheep and the production of karakul, Uzbekistan occupies one of the leading places in the world. The inhabitants of Uzbekistan have been engaged in sheep breeding since ancient times. In Uzbekistan, 15,340.5 thousand heads of sheep and goats are bred (as of January 1, 2011), mainly sheep, including Karakul sheep.

Great damage to sheep breeding is caused by the estrosis disease caused by the larvae of the nasopharyngeal gadfly *Oestrus ovis* L. (DIPTERA: OESTRIDAE), which develop in the nasal and adjacent head cavities of sheep. In Uzbekistan, the locals called this disease “gir-gir”, in Russian “false whirlwind”. The study of the biology and ecology of the nasopharyngeal gadfly *Oestrus ovis* of Karakul sheep and their regional features of the development cycle, make it possible to enhance the effectiveness of anti-estrogenic - preventive measures.

Purpose of the study: Analysis of the studies conducted on the study of nasopharyngeal gadflies *Oestrus ovis* in sheep.

Materials and methods of research: Based on the analysis and the historical and scientific method, the study of the sheep gadfly *Oestrus ovis* and measures to combat them are covered.

Research results and discussion: The sheep gadfly *Oestrus ovis* Line, 1864 belongs to the Arthropoda phylum, the Insecta insect class, the Diptera order Diptera, and the Oestridae family of nasopharyngeal gadflies. Estrosis of sheep is common everywhere where sheep breeding is in the developed countries of the world. All breeds of sheep bred in Uzbekistan suffer from estrosis, especially Karakul sheep. Great economic damage from this invasion consists of a decrease in meat and wool productivity, death and forced slaughter of animals [3].

In the second half of the 20th century, on biology, ecology, phenology and the distribution of the sheep gadfly *O. ovis* and measures to combat them in the CIS countries, including the southeastern regions of Russia, the Caucasus, Kazakhstan and the Republics of Central Asia, many scientists: Blagoveshchensky

N. D. (1937), Gan E.I. (1942), Beklemishev N.V. (1951), Breev K.A. (1975), Grunin K.N. (1956), Dukalov I.A. (1957), Kolomiets Yu.S., Alfimova A.V. (1956), Klenin I.I. (1955), Shcherban N.F. (1968, 1971), Ternovoy V.I. (1971,1972,1968), Semenov P.V. (1981, 1985), Baiburiev M.B. (1986), Marchenko V.A. (1985), Pushkarev A.S. (1986) and others conducted extensive studies [1; 3; 6].

According to H.E. Kocheganova (1963), in some years in the Semipalatinsk region of Kazakhstan, mortality from estrosis reaches 39.5%, sick sheep endured up to 20% of their weight, and weak lambs were born. In studies conducted by M.K. Baiburiyeva (1926) in the Chimkent region, the infection rate of sheep was 83.5% and the intensity was 10.6 larvae. According to R.I. Boldyreva (1933), in the Almaty region, the infection of sheep with gadfly larvae is on average 93% per year [6].

In the Stavropol Territory of Russia, according to V.P. Tolokonnikov (1995, 2005), the flight of the sheep gadfly *O. ovis* begins in June and ends in the third decade of October - the first decade of November. Fertilized females do not fly. Within 10-15 days, larvae are formed in the uterus-shaped receiver. Imago do not feed, live off the nutrients accumulated in the larval phase. After the completion of the larval stage, the females become active and begin to fly. Female gadflies are viviparous, the fecundity of one female is about 700 larvae [1].

V. I. Ternovoy (1985-1995) reports that males live 3-9 days in summer, somewhat longer in autumn. The life expectancy of females in summer is 15-20 days, in autumn - up to 40 days. The duration of development of larvae in the host organism in the North Caucasus during autumn infection is 150-240 days, while in spring it is 30-45 days. According to M.Sh. Akbaeva (2002) Mature larvae of the third stage migrate from the frontal sinuses to the nasal cavity and irritate the mucous membrane, which causes reflex sneezing in sheep, which contributes to the release of parasites into the environment. The larvae penetrate the soil to a depth of 1-5 cm. The pupal phase is 14-16 days. S.P. Kuklin. (1952), I.I. Klenin (1958), Ch.E. Rogers, F.W. Knapp (1973) during studies noted that in the process of

adaptation of the larvae of the 1st stage of *O. ovis* in the host organism, their complete death (up to 90%) occurs in the first days after infection, and only after 20-30 days of the day the death of larvae decreases. According to P.V. Semenov (1987) natural and climatic conditions of the *O. ovis* habitat affect the number of generations per year. In years with one generation, the development of larvae in the body of sheep lasts 8-11 months; with two generations, the duration of the development cycle of larvae of the autumn generation is 8-10 months, spring -1-3. [3].

A number of authors: A.M. Krivko (1956), I.A. Spiruykhov, S.N. Machulisky (1959), Ya.I. Kalkis (1965), A.Yu. Manytskov (1969), I.A. Ponomarev (1971), I.M. Migunov (1971), A.P. Camarli, A.T. Tuganbaev (1972), N.F. Shcherban (1976), P.V. Semenov (1980), G.S. Sivkov (1980) et al. found that the timing of the emergence of larvae of the 3rd stage for pupation depends on the climatic conditions of the insect habitat. In biotopes with the development of one generation of the sheep gadfly, the larvae fall to pupate from April to July. In zones of two generations, the larvae of the first generation leave the host organism in the period from February-March to May-July, the second - from July to September-October [1;4].

The development of two generations of the nasopharyngeal gadfly in the spring-summer period in Uzbekistan is reported by E.I. Gan (1942), in Ukraine - Yu. S. Kolomiets (1956), in Kyrgyzstan - A. Tuganboev (1968), in the desert zone of the North Caucasus N.F. Shcherban, V.I. Ternovoy.

In Uzbekistan, studies of the biology and distribution of the sheep gadfly were carried out in the middle of the last century in the laboratory of General Parasitology of the Research Institute of Zoology and Parasitology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Under the guidance of Professor E.I. Gan, many researchers: M. Kadirova, S. Urokov and others studied the nasopharyngeal gadfly of Karakul sheep [7].

E.I. Gan (1942) studied the morphology and biology of the nasopharyngeal gadfly of Karakul sheep. Sheep gadfly *O. ovis* is a small insect, its size is 9-12

mm. The body is covered with small hairs. The head is large, the abdomen is short and bulging. The head and thorax are not divided into segments, brown-gray in color, the abdomen is yellow-gray, the outside is covered with small sharp hairs.

Insects lay their larvae within 2-4 days. At one time, the female injects 8-12 larvae of the 1st stage into the nasal cavity of the sheep. Larvae of the 1st stage are localized on the inner surface of the inferior turbinates, the nasal septum, the wall of the nasal cavity. They are firmly attached to the mucous membrane of the nasal concha due to good armament. The larvae are well provided with food and oxygen here. The armament of larvae of the 2nd and 3rd stages is weaker, they are localized in the maxillary, frontal sinuses, cavities of the horn processes [2;3].

Conclusion: As a result of global climate change, anthropogenic and environmental factors, in the processes of changing natural and artificial ecosystems, in particular the biology of parasitic arthropods that have existed for a long time on natural pastures, there are changes in their ecology and epizootology of diseases.

A scientific study of the bioecology, distribution and harmfulness of the sheep gadfly in the southern regions of our country, including in the conditions of especially changed agrobiocenoses, has not been carried out over the next 50 years. The study of the distribution, development cycle, ecology and morphobiological and epidemiological features of the nasopharyngeal gadfly *Oestrus ovis* L. (DIPTERA: OESTRIDAE) is of practical importance in veterinary medicine, sanitation and medicine. Therefore, to protect sheep from these diseases, it is necessary to develop and implement innovative, coordinated, environmentally friendly, effective veterinary and sanitary measures against them using modern chemical and biological preparations.

List of used literature

1. Балегга А.А. Патогенетическая сущность функционирования паразитарной системы при эстрозе овец и разработка мер борьбы. АВТОРЕФЕРАТ диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата ветеринарных наук. Ставрополь. 2011. – 16 с.

2. Ган Э.И. Овечий овод - *Oestrus ovis*. Ташкент. Наука. 1953. – 168 с.
3. Лысенко И.О. Особенности биологии и экологии *Oestrus ovis*. Экология животных Юг России: экология, развитие. № 4, 2008. - стр. 128-134.
4. Сивкова Е.И., Хлызова Т.А., Фёдорова О.А. Некоторые аспекты изучения носоглоточных оводов (сем. OESTRIDAE) в Сибири. ВЕСТНИК Оренбургского государственного университета. 2017. № 3 (203). – стр. 81-84.
5. Тулеханов А. Региональные особенности биологии носоглоточного овода *Oestrus ovis* L. на юга-востоке Казахстана и обоснование мер борьбы с ним. АВТОРЕФЕРАТ диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата биологических наук: 03.00.19.-Алматы, 1998. – 22 с.: ил.
6. Ураков С. Двукрылые и клещи-паразиты мелкого рогатого скота Кашкадарынской области Узбекистана. АВТОРЕФЕРАТ диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата биологических наук: 03.00.19-Паразитология. Ташкент, 1973. – 18 с.
7. Bobonazarov G'.Y., Omonova N.R., Rabimova Z.Sh. "STUDY ON THE DISTRIBUTION OF BEE TRACHEA ACARAPIS WOODI TICKS IN BEE YARD OF KASHKADARYA REGION" NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN ENGINEERING RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY [IJIERT] ISSN; 2394-3696 Website: ijiert.org Apr-2021.
8. Рахматуллаев, А. Ю., Давронов, Б. О., Норкobilова, З. Б., & Омонова, Н. Р. (2021). Фауна Дождевых Червей В Узбекистана. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 1(5), 310-314.
9. Orziyevich, Davronov Barno. "Features of the lifestyle of aquatic molluscs of Central Asia." ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11.4 (2021): 837-840.
10. Orziyeva, Y. "Water Molluscs Found in Some Water Basins of Kashkadarya Region." Miasto Przyszłości 27 (2022): 145-148.